

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AN EXTENDED FSLM LEARNING STYLE MODEL

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Abstract:

Learning management system focus on supporting teachers in creating and holding online courses but did not consider individual differences in learners such as leaning styles. The impact of learning styles on learning has recently been the focus of scholars and how it can be supported by learning systems. Adaptive educational systems provide learners with courses that fit their individual needs and characteristics such as their learning styles. This research established 24 learning styles from the 8 learning styles of Felder Silverman model. Learners subjected to the system were tested using Felder Silverman learning style model and the proposed model. Scores were recorded and comparison were made for evaluation.

Introduction

Learning Management Systems (LSMs) have found practical and extensive use in e-learning. A LMS is a standalone or web-based system used to plan, implement, and assess a specific learning process. LMS provides an instructor with a way to create and deliver content, monitor student participation, and assess student performance. LSMs are predominantly used for educational and administrative purposes.

The role of a Learning Management System varies depending on the organization's objectives, online training strategy, and desired outcomes. However, the most common use for LMS software is to deploy and track online training initiatives. Before now, the teacher or tutor had major control on the content and mode of delivery of lectures/courses. Recently there is a gradual shift of learning control to the learners. This is made possible by efficient personalized and adaptive learning management systems. Early Learning Management System can be seen as a vast repository where vast information or resources can be stored, tracked and administered. Recent systems are more personalized.

The term "learning styles" indicate that every student learns differently. Technically, an individual's learning style refers to the preferential way in which the student absorbs, processes, comprehends and retains information. Individual learning styles depend on cognitive, emotional and environmental factors, as well as one's prior experience.

While several learning style theories exist in the literature like the learning style models by [1] and [2], [3] has come to be the most widely used and cited learning styles model in computer-based educational systems. Reasons being that most other learning style models classify learners in few groups, while FSLSM go into details describing the learning style of a learner and

distinguishes between preferences on four dimensions. The FSLSM's four dimensions consist of eight paired styles, namely: *sequential/global*, *sensing/intuitive*, *active/reflective* and *visual/verbal*, where no learner can belong to the two pair at a time [4].

Related work

A number of architectures have been done in the area of learning management systems and e-learning. [5] presented how digital libraries can support e-learning. Digital library and e-learning work together but emphasis has been on e-learning by most researchers and the source where the materials needed can be gotten from are neglected. The objectives are; to show how e-learning can be supported by digital library and the functionality of digital library on e-learning resources; to show the type of e-learning that can be supported by digital library; and to examine how digital libraries are responding to the challenges of delivering core services to e-learners. Technical, references and instructional support was provided to e-learners and the library redefine their values and services, collaborate with users and approach their tasks creatively. This research only focused on how materials needed can be provided for learners, time to be used by each learner to learn was not captures and evaluation of student was not captured.

[6] developed an adaptive mobile-e-learning (A-M-E) adaptive architecture to support flexible learning. The motivation of the paper lies in the blending of the pedagogical approach to support mobile learners and add more flexibility to the learning process. This paper seeks to design and develop the M-E adaptive architecture that blends mobile and e-learning in a single integrated computer-based infrastructure. An application that adapts to the preferred learning styles of students was developed, the

application consists of three components namely the web-based interface, the mobile access interface, and the adaptation mechanism that is used to provide just-in-time tailored content according to students' individual preferences. Identified limitation of this paper include m-learning would not be suitable for reading large files; also, no specific learning style model was used.

In [4] adaptive environment for e-learning courses in the context of e-education is created. The current modelling and discovering users' needs, goals, knowledge preferences and motivations that deal with large volumes of information was the motivation for this paper. The objective of this paper is to create adaptive environment for e-learning courses in the context of e-education also to perform personalizing of distance education system, according to students' learning styles. A generic model and architecture of an adaptive e-learning system was developed by describing the structure of an adaptive course and exemplify correlations among e-learning course content and different learning styles. It would be very useful if a real-time feedback loop between intelligent analysis and the adaptive e-learning system is incorporated in this work.

[7] presented a mathematical view of shortest adaptive learning path in e-learning Systems. The motivation for this work is the challenge of e-learning systems to provide courses that tailored to different students with different learning rate and knowledge degree. This research aims at improving the ability of selecting appropriate learning objects for a specific learner, as well as to select the shortest learning path for that learner so as to present an e-learning system that is both efficient and adaptive. Representative algorithms were selected namely; Eliminating, Optimized Selection and the shortest learning path algorithm in order to obtain the benefits of both. The first step of the approach is to construct a sub graph that

is relevant to a learner. The second step is to augment the sub graph with weights that represent the suitability of learning objects for the learner. The third step is to apply a shortest path algorithm to select an adaptive path that is as suitable and as shortest as possible for the learner. The system was not implemented.

[8] developed a framework for adaptive *e*-learning which automatically generate instructional content that suit the pedagogical preference and cognitive ability of a learner in real time. Two components were developed: Content Analyzer and a Selection Model. The Content Analyzer was used to automatically generate metadata to encapsulate cognitive resources within instructional content. The Selection Model used an evolutionary algorithm to evolve instructional content to a Minimum Expected Learning Experience (MELE) to suit the cognitive ability and pedagogical preference of a learner. The system did not generate a course adapting content to the individual cognitive traits and pedagogic preference of a learner.

[9] presented *e*-Learning personalization based on hybrid recommendation strategy and learning style identification. The aim of this research is for a system to recognize different patterns of learning style and learners' habits through testing the learning styles of learners. Firstly, it processes the clusters based on different learning styles. Next, it analyses the habits and the interests of the learners through mining the frequent sequences. Finally, this system completes personalized recommendation of the learning content according to the ratings of these frequent sequences, provided by the system. However, the learning materials suggested to the learners may not suit the interest of the learners because learning styles of the learners were not taken into consideration

before suggesting the material, therefore makes learning not sustainable.

[10] presented the effectiveness of aural instructions with visualizations in *e*-Learning environments. The challenges faced by novice computer science (CS) students when they start course to acquire the skills required on how to write or compile computer programmers lead to this research work motivated this work. The objectives are to reduce the cognitive load on students' working memory by exploiting the dual sensory channels for information processing; and to investigate the effectiveness of using aural instructions together with visualization in teaching the difficult concepts of data structures to novice computer science students. A prototype learning tool, known as the Data Structure Learning (DSL) tool, was developed and used together with visualizations of algorithms, aural instructions produced faster student response times than did textual instructions. This result suggested that the additional use of the auditory sensory channel did indeed reduce the cognitive load. This research did not make comparison study of students who experience the environment and those who choose not to participate, so as to offer a deeper understanding of how the research affects students' learning experience [11].

[12] developed an Adaptive Learning Management System (ALMS) using semantic web technologies. The authors opined that web-based learning management systems should concentrate on how to satisfy the *e*-learners' requirements. The objective is to extract knowledge from the user's interaction, behaviour, actions and translate them into semantics. It also aims to find the Learner style from the knowledge base and deriving and composing the workflow depending upon the learner style. An intelligent agent was used in each module of the framework to perform reasoning. The conceptual framework ALMS combine

learning style detection, ontology operations and knowledge management for reasoning and dynamic composition of e-learning services. In this work, the learning styles of each learner was extracted but learning objects or services was not provided according to the style of the learner.

[13] developed an adaptive e-Learning environment using learning style recognition. The authors noted that the manner in which the knowledge is been represented, like Bayesian Networks, or normal databases which lacks the required level of expressiveness brought about the research. The aim of the paper is to propose a Semantic Agent Framework for the e-Learning environment to detect individual differences existing among individuals, using their learning styles and also to provide more precision in the recognition of learning style. To achieve dynamic adaptability, data-driven approach and literature-based approach was incorporated by creating an ontological framework for modelling the learner and using fuzzy reasoning engine. Simple rule-based reasoning can be performed on the ontology to extract the required content. The recognized learning style can be stored within the system in the learner database and can be used for further interactions with the learner. Felder-Silverman Learning Style Model (FSLSM) was considered for the analysis. The recognized learning style was stored within the system in the learner database and can be used for further interactions with the learner but was not used so as to determine its effectiveness.

[14] presented a personalized adaptive e-learning approach based on semantic web technology. The paper stated that the recent developments in semantic web technologies heightened the need for online adaptive learning environment. The objective is to present an ontology-based approach to develop adaptive e-learning system based on the design of semantic content, learner and

domain models to tailor the teaching process for individual learner's needs. A model that has three modules was developed, the content, learner and domain modules. The learner model describes learner's characteristics required to deliver tailored content. The domain model consists of some classes and properties to define domain topics and semantic relationships between them. The content model describes the structure of courses and their components. The system was not able to recognize changes in the learner's level of knowledge as they progress from one stage of learning process to the next stage.

[15] did an evaluation of a Moodle based adaptive e-Learning system. The author deduced from reviewed literature that different researchers concentrated on single model of learning styles for student adaptive system. The objective is to identify the student's learning styles tendency through a set of questionnaires and the questionnaire scores will be used by the system as basis to provide learning materials that match students' learning styles i.e. visual, auditory and kinesthetic either globally or sequentially. Two models of learning styles were used, which are VAK and Felder. The VAK learning styles include visual, auditory, and kinesthetic, whereas the Felder learning styles include global and sequential. The extraction of students learning styles was done through questionnaire, but the extraction can be done automatically without the knowledge of the learner. Also, this two-learning style model can be combined for effectiveness, instead of subjecting students to it separately.

[16] compared adaptive learning to traditional learning. This research was carried out to do justification to theoretical conclusion that adaptive learning is better than traditional approach of learning. The aim of the work is to examine completion rates; exercise scores for students assigned adaptive

learning exercises; and compares it with the completion rates and quiz scores for students assigned objective-type quizzes in a university digital literacy course. Two methods are used; the first method adopted a set of interactive exercises that were part of an adaptive learning product developed by the publisher of the textbook used in the course and the second method employed a more traditional approach in which students were assigned a set of quizzes comprised of objective items drawn from a test bank supplied by the textbook publisher. 109 students were used for the adaptive learning testing and another set of 113 students were used for traditional approach testing. The same set of students should be used for both the adaptive learning testing and the traditional approach learning testing.

[17] developed web-based adaptivity learning recourses sequencing model. The *e*-learning now based on learner-oriented platforms and putting student's expectations, motivation, habits, learning styles and needs in center of interest. The objective of this research work is to present the possibilities of integrating educational preferences in the learner's model and detect learner's preferences automatically within *e*-learning systems. Two different presentation style user interface templates were employed, learning materials were created to cater for individual learner preferences. The Felder-Solomon learning style was used to measure the learning style preferences of students. There is no limit on the number of materials that can be recommended for the learner which can lead to the learner having more than enough materials needed and can lead to confusion of which materials to be used. Some related works on adaptivity and personalization in learning management systems (LMS) is presented.

Proposed Model for Identifying Inter-Relationships Between FLSM Dimensions

This model describes the Felder-Silverman learning style model (FLSM) and extends it by designing a framework for identifying more inter-related learning styles of FLSM dimensions from the behaviour and actions of learners. Also, an extended adaptive learning management system is developed. It could be seen that the FLSM is limited to only eight learning styles in four dimensions where no learner could exhibit the two styles in the same dimension. This condition also holds in this research due to proven research on learning styles. However, determination of each learning style for a particular learner is done using an ILS.

The following mappings between the FLSM four dimensions was carried out and investigated to determine the levels and strengths of inter-relationships between learning styles within the four dimensions. These are represented as follows:

Figure 3.2 to 3.7 show the design of the extended mapping between the four dimensions of FLSM.

Figure 3.2: Active Sensing, Active Intuitive, Reflective Sensing, Reflective Intuitive

Figure 3.3: Active Verbal, Active Visual,
Reflective Verbal, Reflective Visual

Figure 3.6: Intuitive Global, Intuitive
Sequential, Sensing Global, Sensing
Sequential

Figure 3.4: Active Global, Active Sequential,
Reflective Global, Reflective Sequential

Figure 3.7: Verbal Global, Verbal Sequential,
Visual Global, Visual Sequential

Figure 3.5: Intuitive Verbal, Intuitive Visual,
Sensing Verbal, Sensing Visual

Figure 3.2 to 3.7: Mapping between four
dimensions of FLSM showing learning
styles

From figure 3.2 to 3.7, show the one-to-one
mapping between the dimensions. Which can
also be explained further using set notation as
follows

$$LS_1 = \{L \mid L \in Ac \wedge L \in Se\}$$

$$LS_2 = \{L \mid L \in Ac \wedge L \in In\}$$

$$LS_3 = \{L \mid L \in Re \wedge L \in Se\}$$

$$LS_4 = \{L \mid L \in Re \wedge L \in In\}$$

$$LS_5 = \{L \mid L \in Ac \wedge L \in Vi\}$$

$$LS_6 = \{L \mid L \in Ac \wedge L \in Ve\}$$

$$LS_7 = \{L \mid L \in Re \wedge L \in Vi\}$$

$$LS_8 = \{L \mid L \in Re \wedge L \in Ve\}$$

$$LS_9 = \{L \mid L \in Ac \wedge L \in Sq\}$$

$$LS_{10} = \{L \mid L \in Ac \wedge L \in Gl\}$$

$$LS_{11} = \{L \mid L \in Se \wedge L \in Sq\}$$

$$LS_{12} = \{L \mid L \in Se \wedge L \in Gl\}$$

$$LS_{13} = \{L \mid L \in Se \wedge L \in Vi\}$$

$$LS_{14} = \{L \mid L \in Se \wedge L \in Ve\}$$

$$LS_{15} = \{L \mid L \in In \wedge L \in Vi\}$$

$$LS_{16} = \{L \mid L \in In \wedge L \in Ve\}$$

$$LS_{17} = \{L \mid L \in Se \wedge L \in Sq\}$$

$$LS_{18} = \{L \mid L \in Se \wedge L \in Gl\}$$

$$LS_{19} = \{L \mid L \in In \wedge L \in Sq\}$$

$$LS_{20} = \{L \mid L \in In \wedge L \in Gl\}$$

$$LS_{21} = \{L \mid L \in Vi \wedge L \in Sq\}$$

$$LS_{22} = \{L \mid L \in Ve \wedge L \in Gl\}$$

$$LS_{23} = \{L \mid L \in Vi \wedge L \in Sq\}$$

$$LS_{24} = \{L \mid L \in Ve \wedge L \in Gl\}$$

$$ELS = \{LS_1, LS_2, \dots, LS_{24}\}$$

where ELS, LS_j(j = 1, 2, 3, ..., 24), and L are extended learning style, learning Style, and learner respectively. Therefore, twenty-four (24) is the maximum number of dimensions and observed behaviour in the proposed enhanced FLSM dimension learner styles. It can be seen that possible interrelationships between the four dimensions of FLSM are twenty-four in number.

Evaluation

The performance evaluation of FLSM model with the proposed model is calculated using T-test Independent Sample Formula

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{S_p^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)}} \sim t_{\alpha/2}(n_1 + n_2 - 2) \quad (1)$$

With

$$S_p^2 = \frac{(n_1 - 1)s_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}$$

Where, \bar{x}_1 is Mean of the proposed model, \bar{x}_2 is Mean of FLSM model, S_1 is Standard deviation of the proposed model, S_2 is Standard deviation of FLSM model, n_1 is Sample size of the proposed model, n_2 is Sample size of FLSM model, S_p^2 is Pooled variance

The formula for standard deviation is given

$$\text{by: } \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2}{n-1}} \quad (3)$$

Where x is values given, \bar{x} is Mean, n is Total number of values,

A random sample of thirty-one (31) students were selected from students of Computer Science department Federal Polytechnic, Ile-Oluji to participate in the learning of four selected courses and the evaluation using online exercises, the exercise scores are recorded and average was calculated with significant level of 0.05, and test if there is any significant difference between the mean of the both model.

Result and Discussion

A total of 31 students of the department of Computer science, Federal Polytechnic Ile-Oluji were registered and participated in the learning process. Four courses

COM 211 (Computer Programming using OO Basic)

COM 212 (Introduction to systems Programming)

COM 213 (File Organization and Management)

COM 214 (Computer Systems Troubleshooting)

were used for evaluating the performance of the system. Learning materials were given to the learners twice and also tested twice. The learning style of each learner were detected using the FSLSM four-dimension learning style and the learning style were used to give learning materials for the learner to learn, thereafter tested on what has been learnt. Also, the proposed system was used to detect the learning style of each learner and learning materials were also given to the learner according to the detected learning style and thereafter the learners were tested. The comparison performance of FSLSM Four-dimension learning style model and the proposed system were shown in table 1. The pictorial diagram of the average comparison performance of all the course were clearly shown using bar chart in the graphs below

Figure 1: Comparison Performance of FSLSM Four-dimension learning style model and the proposed system in an average performance of all the four courses

Conclusion

Learning management system focus on supporting lecturers in creating, administrating and managing online courses but no adaptivity for learners. While adaptive systems support learners by providing courses that are in accordance with their needs and behaviour which are rarely used in practice. This research work is to design learning management system and embed adaptivity based on the learning styles of learners into the system. To provide adaptivity in learning management system, learning styles of learners needed to be known. the relationship between the eight learning styles of FSLSM learning styles was

investigated and extended to 24 learning styles for better learning.

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